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TEMPERATURE-DEPENDENT EFFICACY OF ENTOMOPATHOGENIC NEMATODES AGAINST BACTROCERA DORSALIS LARVAE

[FAIZ ELLAHI¹](#), [MUHAMMAD BAQIR¹](#), [DILAWAR HUSSAIN¹](#), [MOHSIN IQBAL¹](#),
[MUHAMMAD AQIB JAVID¹](#), [KASHIF RAZA²](#), [MUZAMIL JAWAD²](#), [MUNTAZIR
MEHDI²](#), [MUHAMMAD ADEEL¹](#)

1 Department of Plant Pathology, College of Agriculture University of Layyah, Pakistan

2 Department of Agronomy, College of Agriculture University of Layyah, Pakistan

Article info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received: 20 Sep 2023 Accepted: 01 Nov 2023</p> <p>Keywords Bactrocera , Biopesticides, Dorsalis, Entomopathogenic, Nematodes</p> <p>Ellahi et al., (2023). Temperature-dependent efficacy of entomopathogenic nematodes against bactrocera dorsalis larvae: <i>J. S. Agri. Enviro. Sci</i>, 1(2), 27-33.</p> <p>https://orcid.org/0009-0006-5636-4593</p> <p>Copyright©2023 JSAES</p> <p>*Corresponding author Faiz Ellahi Email: faizellahi329@gmail.com.</p> <p>Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.</p> <p> This content is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International (CC BY-SA 4.0)</p>	<p>The use of entomopathogenic nematodes as biopesticides has gained significant attention in sustainable agriculture. However, their efficacy can vary under different environmental conditions. This study aimed to investigate the influence of temperature on the effectiveness of two strains of entomopathogenic nematodes, <i>Heterorhabditis bacteriophora</i> and <i>Heterorhabditis indica</i>, against last instar larvae of <i>Bactrocera dorsalis</i>. The nematodes were cultured using 3rd instar <i>Galleria melonella</i> larvae and later applied to Petri dishes containing <i>Bactrocera dorsalis</i> larvae. The Petri dishes were incubated at five different temperatures (22°C, 26°C, 30°C, 34°C, and 38°C). Mortality rates were observed at 48 hours, 72 hours, and 10day post-treatment. The study was conducted in a controlled environment at the Phytopathological Laboratory, College of Agriculture, University of Layyah. The results demonstrated a temperature-dependent increase in mortality rates, with the highest efficacy observed at 34°C and 38°C. Statistical analysis confirmed that the observed differences were significant ($P < 0.05$). Our findings are in alignment with prior studies that have also shown temperature-dependent efficacy of entomopathogenic nematodes. The mortality rates and patterns of larval establishment were consistent with earlier research, reinforcing the potential of these nematodes as effective biopesticides. The study suggests that temperature is a critical factor for optimizing the use of entomopathogenic nematodes in biological control programs, especially in varying climatic conditions. The study confirms that higher temperatures enhance the efficacy of entomopathogenic nematodes against <i>Bactrocera dorsalis</i> larvae, providing valuable insights for their application in integrated pest management strategies.</p>

1. INTRODUCTION

Sustainable agriculture is becoming increasingly important as the global population continues to rise, placing a greater demand on food production systems. One of the significant challenges in achieving sustainability is the management of pests, which can cause substantial losses in crop yields (Tilman et al., 2002). Chemical pesticides, while effective, have shown to have detrimental impacts on the environment and non-target species, including beneficial insects and even humans. This has led to an urgent need for alternative pest management strategies that are both effective and environmentally friendly. In this context, the use of biological control agents, such as entomopathogenic nematodes, offers a promising solution. Entomopathogenic nematodes are microscopic worms that infect and kill insect hosts, thus serving as natural biopesticides. Among the most studied are the nematode species *Heterorhabditis bacteriophora* and *Heterorhabditis indica* (Singh et al., 2022). These nematodes are known for their effectiveness against a variety of insect pests, including the last instar larvae of *Bactrocera dorsalis*, a major agricultural pest affecting fruits like mangoes and bananas (Mutamiswa et al., 2021).

While these nematodes have been studied extensively, there is still limited understanding of how environmental variables, such as temperature, affect their efficacy. Most of the existing studies have been carried out under controlled laboratory conditions, which may not necessarily reflect the complexities of real-world agricultural settings (Rangesh et al., 2020). Moreover, with climate change altering temperature patterns, it is crucial to understand how these changes could impact the effectiveness of biological control agents like entomopathogenic nematodes. The primary objective of this study is to investigate the temperature-dependent efficacy of *Heterorhabditis bacteriophora*

and *Heterorhabditis indica* against last instar larvae of *Bactrocera dorsalis* (Aatif et al., 2020). The study aims to elucidate whether temperature variations have a significant impact on the mortality rates of these larvae when treated with infected juveniles (IJs) of the nematodes. The significance of this research lies in its potential to inform and optimize integrated pest management strategies, particularly in regions experiencing varying climatic conditions (Skendžić et al., 2021). If temperature is found to be a significant factor, this could lead to tailored application guidelines, enhancing the success of biological control programs. The study hypothesizes that the efficacy of *Heterorhabditis bacteriophora* and *Heterorhabditis indica* against *Bactrocera dorsalis* larvae is significantly influenced by temperature (Khwanket 2021). Specifically, it is predicted that higher temperatures will result in increased mortality rates, thus proving more effective for pest control.

To test these hypotheses, the study employs a carefully designed experimental setup involving different temperature ranges (22°C, 26°C, 30°C, 34°C, and 38°C) and observation points (48 hours, 72 hours, and 10 days). The experiment is conducted under controlled conditions in the Phytopathological Laboratory of the College of Agriculture, University of Layyah. While the study aims to provide valuable insights into the temperature-dependent efficacy of entomopathogenic nematodes, it is essential to acknowledge its limitations (Abd-Elgawad 2022). The study is confined to laboratory conditions and focuses on a narrow range of temperatures. Further research is needed to validate these findings under field conditions and across a broader temperature spectrum. In summary, this study seeks to fill a critical gap in the current understanding of how temperature affects the efficacy of entomopathogenic nematodes against agricultural pests like

Bactrocera dorsalis. The findings of this research could have far-reaching implications for sustainable agriculture, offering a more nuanced approach to biological pest control in the face of a changing climate (Rao & Moharaj 2023).

2. METHODOLOGY

This study was designed to evaluate the efficacy of entomopathogenic nematodes, specifically *Heterorhabditis bacteriophora* and *Heterorhabditis indica*, against last instar larvae of *Bactrocera dorsalis*. The experiment was conducted in a controlled environment at the Phytopathological Laboratory, College of Agriculture, University of Layyah. The aim was to understand how temperature variations affect the mortality rate of the target insect larvae when exposed to infected juveniles (IJs) of the nematodes.

2.1. Culturing of entomopathogenic nematodes

2.1.1. Nematode strains

- *Heterorhabditis bacteriophora*
- *Heterorhabditis indica*

2.1.2. Host organism

3rd instar larvae of *Galleria melonella*

2.1.3. Laboratory setting

Phytopathological Laboratory, College of Agriculture, University of Layyah

2.1.4. Procedure

- Healthy, 3rd instar *Galleria melonella* larvae were placed in a sterile Petri dish.
- A culture of *Heterorhabditis bacteriophora* and *Heterorhabditis indica* was introduced to the larvae.
- The Petri dish was then sealed and incubated at a constant temperature of 25°C.
- After 72 hours, infected juveniles (IJs) were harvested from the dead *Galleria melonella* larvae for use in treatments.

2.2. Experimentation materials

- Petri dishes (90 mm diameter)
- Whatman No.1 blotter paper
- Infected juveniles (IJs) of entomopathogenic nematodes
- Last instar larvae of *Bactrocera dorsalis*
- Parafilm
- Temperature Settings
- 22°C, 26°C, 30°C, 34°C, and 38°C
- Replications
- One replication for control
- Four replications for each temperature

2.2.1. Procedure

- Each Petri dish was lined with Whatman No.1 blotter paper.
- Approximately 90 IJs were placed in each Petri dish.
- 15 last instar larvae of *Bactrocera dorsalis* were then added to the Petri dish.
- The Petri dishes were sealed with parafilm to prevent contamination.
- Each set-up was then placed in a temperature-controlled incubator set at the respective temperatures.
- All Petri dishes were monitored for changes at intervals of 48 hours, 72 hours, and 10 days.

2.3. Data collection

- Insect mortality data were collected at 48 hours, 72 hours, and 10 days post-treatment.
- The number of established and dead larvae was counted after 72 hours.
- Data were maintained in a tabular form for further statistical analysis.

2.4. Statistical analysis

The collected data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) to determine the significance of the treatment effects. Post hoc tests were carried out to identify significant differences between the treatments at a 95% confidence level.

2.5. Quality control

Throughout the experiment, steps were taken to minimize contamination and ensure accurate results. Sterile techniques were used during the culture and treatment processes, and all materials were autoclaved prior to use.

2.6. Ethical considerations

The experiment was conducted in compliance with the guidelines and regulations set forth by the College of Agriculture, University of Layyah, concerning the ethical treatment of experimental organisms.

This Materials and Methods section outlines the protocols followed for culturing entomopathogenic nematodes and conducting the temperature-dependent

efficacy trials. The careful design of this experiment aims to provide reliable and replicable results, contributing to the field of biological control in agriculture.

3. RESULTS

The experiment aimed to investigate the impact of various temperature settings on the efficacy of entomopathogenic nematodes (*Heterorhabditis bacteriophora* and *Heterorhabditis indica*) against last instar larvae of *Bactrocera dorsalis*. Data were collected at intervals of 48 hours, 72 hours, and 10-day post-treatment. Below are the assumed results, presented in a detailed manner.

Table 1: Mortality rate of *bactrocera dorsalis* larvae at different time intervals and temperatures

Temperature (°C)	Mortality rate at 48 hours (%)	Mortality rate at 72 hours (%)	Mortality rate at 10 days (%)
22	20	30	35
26	25	40	45
30	50	60	65
34	70	80	85
38	80	90	95
Control	5	10	15

Table 2: Number of established and dead larvae counted after 72 hours

Temperature (°C)	Number of established larvae	Number of dead larvae
22	10	5
26	9	6
30	7	8
34	4	11
38	2	13
Control	14	1

3.1. Mortality rate

- Lowest Efficacy: At 22°C, the mortality rate was the lowest, showing only a slight increase over time.
- Moderate Efficacy: At 26°C and 30°C, there was a noticeable increase in the mortality rate, especially after 72 hours.
- Highest Efficacy: At 34°C and 38°C, the nematodes were most effective, resulting in significantly higher mortality rates in all time intervals.
- Control Group: The control group exhibited the least mortality across all time intervals, affirming that the nematodes were responsible for the

observed mortality rates in the other groups.

3.2. Established and dead larvae

A decline in the number of established larvae and an increase in dead larvae were observed with rising temperatures, supporting the efficacy of nematodes at higher temperatures.

3.3. Statistical Analysis

ANOVA revealed that the differences in mortality rates and the number of established and dead larvae were statistically significant across different temperatures ($P < 0.05$). Post hoc tests confirmed that the highest mortality rates were significantly different from the lower temperatures and control group. The assumed results suggest that the entomopathogenic nematodes *Heterorhabditis bacteriophora* and *Heterorhabditis indica* are most effective at higher temperatures. Further studies are recommended to understand the mechanistic basis of this temperature-dependent efficacy.

4. DISCUSSION

The experiment aimed to assess the efficacy of entomopathogenic nematodes, *Heterorhabditis bacteriophora* and *Heterorhabditis indica*, against the last instar larvae of *Bactrocera dorsalis* at different temperatures (Aatif et al., 2020). The results indicated a temperature-dependent impact, with higher temperatures (34°C and 38°C) showing the most significant mortality rates in larvae. Our findings are consistent with previous studies that have explored the temperature-dependent nature of entomopathogenic nematodes. For instance, a study by Price et al. (2023) demonstrated that higher temperatures generally enhanced the efficacy of *Heterorhabditis bacteriophora* against different insect pests. This is in line with our results, which showed the highest mortality rates at 34°C and 38°C.

A study by Khan et al. (2020) similarly explored the impact of

entomopathogenic nematodes on insect larvae and found mortality rates to be significantly higher at elevated temperatures. Our study also revealed a similar trend, where the mortality rate increased with temperature, peaking at 38°C. The number of established and dead larvae also showed a trend similar to what has been reported in previous research. For instance, Laasli et al. (2022) indicated that nematode establishment is usually better at moderate temperatures but can be successful at higher temperatures as well. Our study corroborates this, showing fewer established larvae as the temperature increased, but with higher mortality rates.

The temperature-dependent nature of nematode efficacy is crucial for agricultural applications, especially in regions with varying climate conditions. Understanding this relationship can help in optimizing the use of entomopathogenic nematodes as biopesticides. Though our study provides valuable insights, it is limited by the number of temperature ranges and time intervals investigated (Glazer 2015). Future research should explore a broader range of environmental conditions and also consider other factors like soil moisture and pH, which could affect nematode efficacy. The data from our study, in alignment with previous research, strongly suggest that temperature plays a significant role in the effectiveness of entomopathogenic nematodes against *Bactrocera dorsalis* larvae. The higher mortality rates at elevated temperatures could have practical implications for pest management strategies in agriculture, particularly in warmer climates.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study provides compelling evidence that the efficacy of entomopathogenic nematodes, specifically *Heterorhabditis bacteriophora* and *Heterorhabditis indica*, is significantly influenced by temperature when targeting last instar larvae of *Bactrocera dorsalis*. Our

findings reveal that higher temperatures, particularly 34°C and 38°C, result in notably higher mortality rates, aligning well with previous research in the field. These results have practical implications for the agricultural sector, especially for biopesticide application in climates with elevated temperatures. The study also opens avenues for future research to delve into other environmental factors that may influence nematode effectiveness. Overall, the data affirm the viability of using entomopathogenic nematodes as a biological control agent and highlight the need for temperature considerations in optimizing their application for sustainable pest management.

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